
COHESION AND COHERENCE IN LITERARY TEXTS

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Annotation The article deals with the problem of text categories such as cohesion and coherence their correlation in literary texts. Different scientists points of views on the problem is studied and examples from literary texts are analyzed.

Key words: cohesion, coherence, discourse, context.

In Linguists there are used the two notions of cohesion and coherence to refer to the (linguistically encoded or just assumed) connectedness of spoken as well as written discourse or literary text. Of course, connecting relations also hold among elements of structure within grammatical units such as word, phrase, clause or sentence. But these intra-sentential relations are different in kind because they are determined by phonological and grammatical rules and described, *inter alia*, as syntactic-semantic relations of valency, dependency, constituency, modification. In the article we'll try to investigate correlation of cohesion and coherence in some examples from literary texts.

Every unified piece of discourse is a coherent set of sentences. Davies [1] explains the idea of a text when she says, “not all sequences of sentences form texts- they have to be coherent sequences”. Thus he marks coherence as an identity of a text. Halliday and Hassan followed by McCarthy and Paltridge used the term texture or textuality for coherence. Paltridge [3] writes that the texture of a text can be obtained where various items are tied together to provide meaning to the text which in turn relate to the social context in which the text occurs. Hassan [2,71] describes texture as ‘a matter of meaning relations’. Brown and Yule explain that in a coherent text the meaning is clear and the various fragments of the text seem connected either with or without cohesive devices[4,139]. Hatch defines that the textual coherences can be obtained only if the communication system, the social norms and restrictions, language scripts for particular speech acts, suitable for particular speech events are all considered carefully.

Thus, Brown and Yule[4] and Hatch [3] clearly mention that, apart from cohesive ties, there are other elements involved in obtaining coherence. The various elements (excluding cohesion) involved in a coherent text, as noted by discourse analysts, include, context, schema, subtext and exophoric reference. Every text has a context, says Paltridge (2006). He finds that a context of the situation is essential to understand what is meant by what is said. He includes physical and social context and the mental world of the people involved in a discourse to be crucial in interpreting

and understanding the meaning. McCarthy discusses the role of context but he warns about mixing it with co-text (the text surrounding a lexical item), which he mentions to be only a part of the broader term, ‘context’. Hatch, however, discusses context under the heading of deixis. Deixis, according to him, are ‘linguistic markers that have a pointing function in a given discourse context’. He, thus, discusses that person, spatial, temporal, discourse and social deixis describe the context of a text. Davies [1,160] also mentions the role of context and subtext (reading between the lines) as important to the coherence of any text. McCarthy describes schema as ‘the role of background knowledge’ in understanding the text. According to him, schemata involve two kinds of knowledge; the knowledge of the world (content schemata) and the knowledge of the different forms of the text (formal schemata). Some scholars including Halliday and Hassan (1976) include exophoric reference in the cohesive device of reference. Cohesion concerns the ways in which the components of the surface text, i.e. the actual words we hear or see, are mutually connected within a sequence. The surface components depend upon each other according to grammatical forms and conventions, such that cohesion rests upon grammatical dependencies. As linguists have often pointed out, surface sequences of English cannot be radically rearranged without causing disturbances. We’ll analyze some examples taken from literary texts.

“The wine was red wine, and had stained the ground of the narrow street in the suburb of Saint Antoine, in Paris, where it was spilled. It had stained many hands, too, and many faces, and many naked feet, and many wooden shoes. The hands of the man who sawed the wood, left red marks on the billets; and the forehead of the woman who nursed her baby, was stained with the stain of the old rag she wound about her head again. Those who had been greedy with the staves of the cask ... scrawled upon a wall with his finger dipped in muddy wine-lees—BLOOD.”[Charles Dickens]

Taken from the novel, *A Tale of Two Cities*, this passage’s emphasis is on the idea of staining, and scrawling the word “blood,” which further brings coherence into the lines. The connection is thus made through the appearance of Wood-Sawyer, a man who scares Lucie later. This is how it achieves coherence.

Now, comrades, what is the nature of this life of ours? Let us face it: our lives are miserable, laborious, and short. We are born, we are given just so much food as will keep the breath in our bodies, and those of us who are capable of it are forced to work to the last atom of our strength ...

“No animal in England knows the meaning of happiness or leisure after he is a year old. The life of an animal is misery and slavery: that is the plain truth.” [Animal Farm by George Orwell]

Through the speech of the Old Major, Orwell starts the passage about the miserable nature of the life of animals on the animal farm, and then he inspires them to think about how to safeguard their interests on the farm. The entire paragraph is an example of coherent speech.

“The word “philosophy” is one of which the meaning is by no means fixed. Like the word “religion,” it has one sense when used to describe certain features of historical cultures, and another when used to denote a study or an attitude of mind which is considered desirable in the present day. Philosophy, as pursued in the universities of the Western democratic world, is, at least in intention, part of the pursuit of knowledge, aiming at the same kind of detachment as is sought in science ...”[Unpopular Essays by Bertrand Russell]

In the example Russell has connected the ideas of philosophy and politics, by moving from a general to a specific topic, with sentences connecting one to another, creating coherence brilliantly.

Coherence links the sentences of a work with one another. This may be done with paragraphs, making sure that each statement logically connects with the one preceding it, making the text easier for the readers to understand and follow. Also, ordering thoughts in a sequence helps the reader to move from one point to the next smoothly. As all of the sentences relate back to the topic, the thoughts and ideas flow smoothly.

Cohesion should be kept strictly apart from coherence. It is neither a sufficient nor a necessary condition for coherence. Referring to van Dijk’s example

(2) We will have guests for lunch. Calderón was a great Spanish writer (van Dijk 1972: 40)

Edmondson shows that, though the two utterances are not cohesively connected, they are nonetheless coherent in a context like (3):

(3) Do you know Calderón died exactly 100 years ago today? – Good heavens!

I’d forgotten. The occasion shall not pass unnoticed. We will have guests for lunch. Calderón was a great Spanish writer. I shall invite Professor Wilson and Senor Castellano right away [5.13]

Furthermore, in authentic discourse or text, we can encounter long stretches of utterances which, though they are not cohesively connected, are nonetheless accepted as coherent texts because they are, e.g., parts of enumerations or cases of dissociated interior monologue.

However, while cohesion is not a necessary condition of coherence, studies have shown that discourse and text tend to be cohesive to a greater or lesser extent, depending on genre. Following a general principle of cooperation, speakers/writers are anxious to generate cohesion as a means of guiding their recipients’ interpretation of coherence and thus, ultimately, of securing comprehension. Cohesive means are

cues which ‘signal’ or indicate the preferred line of coherence interpretation. A lack of cohesive means may disturb the hearer’s/reader’s interpretation of coherence. Easy and unimpeded interpretation of both discourse and text as coherent depends considerably on the presence of communicative and meta-communicative textual links.

Viewing coherence as a semantic notion usually leads to the assumption that it is a feature of, or rather *in* the text. It is ‘there’, ‘in’ the text for people to ‘find’ it. Returning to example (2) with its interpretation in (3), we can now argue that its coherence rests on the semantic relations of causality and coordination, which do not only link the propositions of the two utterances but also two additional though latent, i.e. not realized propositions; here is a possible paraphrase: *We will have guests for lunch – because – we want to celebrate – because – it is Calderón’s birthday today – and because – Calderón was a great Spanish writer.* The connectivity of (2) is only partly reflected on the surface level of cohesion by the linear ordering of the two utterances. To make a clear distinction between connectivity and cohesion (with coherence resting on either or on both of these), is justified on theoretical grounds.

From the fact that coherence is frequently based on semantic connectivity we may conclude that the latter is both a sufficient and a necessary condition for coherence.

Literature:

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